

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: KUEK****FIRST NAME: SHERMAN****PROGRAM CODE: DRCTh****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)The author used the following software: MSWord 2019 on a Macbook

THE ART OF IDEATION

1) INTRODUCTION

The *ACA-401D Coursepack Period 1* is a compilation of stipulations for clear and substantial basics of academic work. Like any other field of specialisation, academic writing requires systematic methodology which must include planning and execution. This compilation of guidelines provides a rather comprehensive description of how one begins the process of planning, moves on to the research phase of study, and eventually culminates in writing and the final editing of one's academic essay (EUCLID 2019, 1-4).

At the same time, the *Coursepack* also belabours the reality that academic research and writing comes with inherent pitfalls that must be avoided if one is to uphold the integrity of this field of work. To that end, it tediously spells out various aspects of the research and writing process that we must be cautious to address. This includes the need to acknowledge other authors upon whose ideas we build ours, to follow international grammatical conventions, and to be consistent in the style of our writing as well as our use of the English language. Of particular importance are the detailed "dos and don'ts" to be observed by the freshly initiated researcher and writer.

2) NEEDFUL REMINDERS

Academic writing is not new to me, considering that I have been through extensive postgraduate studies in the past years. However, this does not mean that there are no essential aspects of academic research and writing that I am inclined to overlook either by force of habit or by sheerly being out of touch with the latest progress in academic

methodologies. Period 1 reading has therefore proven profitable for me as I find myself being reminded of some crucial guidelines that I need to carry with me for the rest of my duration in this course of studies and beyond it.

a) Giving Credit Where is Due

I am reminded that there is probably no such thing as an entirely original idea unless one is an Einstein-level genius. The rest of us can only stand on the shoulders of giants in our academic pursuits. Because of this, it is absolutely vital for us to incorporate extensive “reading and researching” into the development of an essay (EUCLID 2019, 2). This would ensure that there is an intellectual exchange and a cross-pollination of ideas in the contents of our essay. In this regard, I am fortunate that the nature of my work involves continual research that requires extensive reading and thinking.

I also note that serious caution has been offered repeatedly in the reading assignment on giving credit to authors upon whose ideas ours are built (EUCLID 2019, 5, 16). I hasten to add to this caution that it is equally crucial for us to understand the theses and arguments of those other authors when we interact with their ideas. In my experience as an academic teacher, many students have written their assignments in seeming full compliance to the warning against plagiarism. The point at which they fail, however, is that of truly understanding the ideas of the scholars they have quoted and acknowledged in their writing. The principle of academic justice should be consistently carried out by not just acknowledging the source of an idea but also demonstrating adequate comprehension of the idea itself.

b) Ensuring Clarity in Communication

While having substance in our research is crucial, it is equally important to write well by presenting our arguments in a clear and convincing manner. The reader of our paper ought not to be left unclear about what the paper seeks to achieve and the direction in which the writer’s arguments are going (EUCLID 2019, 14). I remember being taught as a young doctoral student in seminary that every dissertation must have a clearly stated thesis, and that the thesis statement must be supported by a number of strongly evidenced arguments. In the same way, our reading of all academic literature is essentially an exploration of the authors’ theses and their arguments supporting those theses statements. According to my professor, the point at which a piece of academic writing fails is when the author’s thesis is not immediately clear, which in turn renders all his/her arguments potentially redundant.

But there is more that makes for good writing than a mere clearly stated thesis statement and its accompanying arguments. A writer should also be able to hold the reader’s attention through a crafty but appropriate use of language (EUCLID 2019, 15). As a writer who publishes religious teachings for reading among non-academicians, I have always been aware of the necessity to write in a way that sustains the imagination of the lay reader. Among the various aspects that need my attention in order to ensure the

effectiveness of this endeavour, the use of proper punctuations and grammar is certainly a crucial one (EUCLID 2019, 17). This is so that my communication of ideas will be efficacious and not be in danger of being misconstrued. I come from a field of study which contains a memory of a historical event during which a single letter “i” made a difference in a word that caused a major disagreement between two groups of scholars.

c) Preserving Consistency of Style

I very much acknowledge the need for the adoption of a particular style of academic writing for the purpose of consistency and coherence (EUCLID 2019, 24). This is necessary in order that readers who are attempting to understand our writing do not get lost in a convolution of inconsistencies. When there is consistency of style, it gets the confusion and distraction out of the way and enables the reader to focus on the immediate matter of concern, that is, the topic of discussion advanced in the writing.

However, while I acknowledge that consistency of style is important, I have always found myself entertaining a nagging concern. It has often somewhat disturbed me that an over-emphasis on strict adherence to a particular style of writing may impede my creative expression as a writer. It is probably a challenge for every writer to maintain a healthy balance between consistency and creativity by finding a point of convergence between the two aspects such that they need not be mutually exclusive in relation to each other.

Having said that, one reminder that I deeply value in the course of this reading pertaining to consistency in writing style is that of keeping my sentences short (EUCLID 2019, 14). During my days as a young university student, I spent some time being interned at a legal firm and became heavily influenced by the length of sentences found in the legal agreements that I had to type out daily. I have since found it a great challenge to reverse this habitual inclination.

d) Acknowledging the Impact of a Colonial Past

Despite the fact that American English is more significantly used than British English (EUCLID 2019, 27), I have grown up in a land that was colonised by the British. When I was a young schoolboy, my teachers had always insisted that my spelling of words should always be in accordance with British English. His famous admonishment, “We are not American!” still rings in my ears even today. Furthermore, my parents studied under the British education system and trained me in the same manner. Subsequently, my bachelor’s degree was also conferred by a British university. For this reason, I do admit that I have a strong gravitation towards the use of British rather than American English.

However, this does not mean that my daily expressions in speech and writing are totally consistent with the British style, as I am certain that I have come to unintentionally incorporate even American elements into my daily expressions. A typical example I have found rather hilarious in the course readings is the use of the word “trousers” as opposed to “pants”, because this precisely describes my unintentional confusion (EUCLID 2019,

29)! In fact, as I watch movies, I have also come to a realisation that this mix-up is rather pronounced even among native British speakers these days. A case in point is how many British actors are pronouncing the word “either” in the American rather than the traditional British way. I personally surmise that this is the outcome of a globalised world. All this perhaps points to a need for me to broaden my horizons by being more open to ways of expressing language preferences that I may not have been entirely comfortable with before. Interestingly, my wife, who holds a master’s degree in the English language, insists that there is not one “English language”, but rather, many “English languages”. I should perhaps strive to embrace her inclusive attitude where language is concerned.

e) Upholding Currency of Expression

The use of plain language is crucial to the extent that clarity in communication is a non-negotiable today (EUCLID 2019, 56). It seems to be that there used to be an era when the extensive use of jargon demonstrated exclusive authority in one’s field of specialisation. These days, such a way of communicating ideas has come to be viewed with disdain, and rightly so, since it contradicts the intrinsic need of every field of knowledge to propagate itself. In fact, many contemporary scholars that I know how come to view the excessive use of jargon as an undue expression of elitism.

However, in the light of my own field of specialisation, that is Roman Catholic Theology, there will be times when expressions are more aptly communicated in Latin, considering that Latin is the official language of the Church of Rome. Furthermore, terms such as *a priori* and *a posteriori*, for example, despite being foreign to most learners, are quite intrinsic to the study of philosophical language frequently employed in the study of Theology (EUCLID 2019, 59). Thus, one may not be able to avoid using such jargon in certain fields of study. Otherwise, I am in full agreement that, as far as possible, terms be communicated in the simplest and most comprehensible manner.

3) CONCLUDING THOUGHTS

I am certain that this compilation of research and writing guidelines will be useful for me in the courses to come, and certainly throughout my dissertation journey. I will undoubtedly have to revisit the guidelines prescribed in the course, not just several but many times, throughout my pilgrimage as a writer. In addition to that, I have found that the accompanying tutorial video prepared by Professor Laurent Cleenewerck is a truly effective pedagogy in helping learners who are less initiated in EUCLID’s system, especially those who are more visual-oriented in their learning inclinations, to internalise the operative instructions on academic writing.

At the same time, as it has been for me in the past, my reunion with this arena of writing conventions and guidelines provokes me to think all over again about whether research and writing constitutes a science or an art, or perhaps a little bit of both. I am not in a rush to derive a terminal conclusion to this question, and I am looking forward to the

few years that I have to allow these thoughts to continue accompanying me towards the completion of my dissertation process.

REFERENCES

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